

WOOD STOCK

Reviewing material intensities, technologies, characteristics, product and building design with underutilised wood in HORIZON project WoodStock

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WOOD STOCK

Empowering climate-smart, circular, and zero-waste use of underutilised wood from the forest and building stock in the construction sector to support the New European Bauhaus

1 November 2024 - 31 October 2028

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-5 – Climate-smart use of wood in the construction sector to support the New European Bauhaus

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UNDERUTILISED WOOD

Hardwood

Low-quality wood

Damaged wood

Post-consumer and residual wood

OUR AMBITIONS

- quantify and map wood resources through material flows, carbon accounting and environmental impact
- develop zero-waste, healthy product, and building solutions
- provide holistic frameworks for policy, innovation, and market development
- establish a European Wood Construction Observatory

SIX LIVING LABS

InnoRenew
UP

The Green Village
TUD

Living Lab GALWAY
GALWAY

Resilient Habitat
UBx

Trondheim Living
Lab NTNU

Living Lab TUL
TUL

Co-creation of circular wood products

CLASSIFICATION OF UNDERUTILISED WOOD STOCKS

- Defined what we mean by underutilised wood
- Compiled evidence on the characteristics, challenges and potential of 4 key underutilised wood stocks

CHARACTERISTICS OF UNDERUTILISED WOOD STOCKS

- Analyzed mechanical, physical properties and processibility of 22 stocks and plotted them on Ashby style plots

Material intensities in the building stock

- Gap: Little information on how much wood there is in buildings
- To get this information, we use *material intensity* (MI) values:

$$\text{Floor area [m}^2\text{]} \times \text{MI [kg/m}^2\text{]}$$

- WoodStock report: data on wooden MI values from 31 studies in Europe
- Values grouped by regions, construction types, and elements.

Regions

Material intensities in the building stock

BUT more wood in light timber frame larger than CLT?

Not really!

Review of new technologies and processes

Technology areas

- Scanning
- Data analytics and AI
- Data storage, tagging systems
- Software solutions
- Automated tools
- Primary raw material processing
- Networks that connect these processes

6 Phases of technology - Divided by primary raw material (PRM) and as a post-consumer wood (PCW).

Non-Destructive Assessment of Reclaimed Timber Elements

X-ray CT Scanning

Computational modelling

Engraved QR codes - materials passports for circular construction

cea CEA - DOME1

Component AA-000

Life Cycle	CID	Project Name	Project Location	Install Date	Removal Date	Material	Material Sub-Type	Height (cm)	Width (cm)	Length (cm)	Weight (kg)	Condition
1	:S-AA14:	Musikpavilion	Oetwil am See, CH	unknown	08.06.2022	Wood	Pine	12	12	180	10.88	Good
2	:S-AA14<_S-AA000:	Swiss Sustainability Forum	Bern, CH	22.09.2022	unknown	Wood	Pine	12	12	180	10.88	Good

Review of zero-waste product concepts

● Identification:

- Over 190 products and prototypes identified
 - Developed in academia and by industry, different TRLs
 - Classification into linear (1D), planar (2D), and volumetric (3D) elements
- Strategies for designing with underutilised wood:
 - 10 recurring design strategies identified and formulated
 - Ranging from hyper-local, craft-based approaches to those integrated within industrial systems
- Evaluation through the NEB lens:
 - Qualitative evaluation framework defined based on NEB-Compass, specified for timber building through indicators
 - 17 case studies evaluated in relation to Beautiful, Together and Sustainable values

Design strategy: Embracing irregularity

- Accepting variations in geometry, dimensions, or finishes.
- Prioritising minimal processing to preserve material integrity and reduce waste.

Wood Chip Barn. 2016. Design: AA Hooke Park Design + Make students.
Photographs: Valerie Bennett. UK.

Office by Nature. 2026. Studio Massimo.
The Netherlands.

Design strategy: Homogenisation & standardisation

- Transforming heterogeneous materials into uniform components
- Reprocessing, hybridisation, or integration in engineered wood products
- Repeatabile modular parts with consistent sizes and performance aligned with industrial norms.

The Urban Woods. CLT with reclaimed pallets and ash. 2026.
Urban Climate Architects. The NL.

TRIQBRIQ. Modular building blocks
from underused wood. 2025.
Germany.

BurntWood ReUse cladding. Denmark.

Review of zero-waste building concepts

- 103 case studies that demonstrate strategies for using underutilised wood stocks

KEVN
Superuse

NEB compass

International Survey on wood perception

GET INVOLVED!

Join the WoodStock Connect Network

- newsletter (twice per year)
- invitations to WoodStock events

Social media:

@woodstock_project

@woodstock_horizonproject (insta)

www.woodstockproject.eu

WOODSTOCK GRANTS

€200,000 FOR INNOVATION IN CLIMATE-SMART CONSTRUCTION

- 4 grants (max. €50,000 per grant)
- for (consortia led by) European SMEs
- projects that use underutilised wood in construction beyond TRL5
- Info sessions (online, 1h)
 - 5 June 2026, 13:00
 - 1 September 2026, 13:00

CALL OPENS
15 SEP 2026

CALL CLOSES
15 DEC 2026

APPLY NOW!

WOOD
STOCK